

Supporting Information

Sodium-Manganese Oxides in Faradaic Desalination: Achieving Long-Cycling Stability through Morphological and Structural Optimization

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S1. Structural characterization

Figure S1. XRD patterns of a) $\text{Na}_{0.44}\text{MnO}_2$ and b) $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{MnO}_{2+\delta}$.

Figure S2. (a) ARM200cF STEM results of mp-NMO-P1 at 200 kV (Manganese oxidation state was calculated using the L23 ratio. Results correspond to the average value of all pixels in each line scan). (b) JEOL JEM-2100 TEM results of mp-NMO-P2 in which the interplanar distance of 6.34 Å corresponds to the b parameter of the NaMnO₂ orthorhombic phase.

Figure S3. Adsorption isotherms of NMO materials.

Figure S4. DFT pore size distribution curve of mp-NMO (obtained with TriStar II Plus software).

Figure S5. Particle size histogram and log-normal distribution for the (a) length and (b) height of the mp-NMO samples.

Table S1. ICP-OES results obtained from Perkin Elmer Optima 7300 CV

Sample	ICP-OES results			Calculated moles		
	Na (wt.%)	Mn (wt.%)	Na/Mn	Mol Na	Mol Mn	Mol O
mp-NMO	20 ± 3.0	50.3 ± 2.5	0.398	1	1.05	2.13
Na _{0.44} MnO ₂	11.8 ± 0.6	60.6 ± 3.0	0.195	1	2.16	3.38
Na _{0.7} MnO _{2+δ}	14.9 ± 0.8	52.7 ± 2.6	0.283	1	1.48	3.11

S2. Electrochemical characterization**Figure S7.** A) CVs at different scan rates of the purely DLC electrodes composed by the current collector, conductive additive and binder. B) The calculated capacitance normalized by electrode mass at different scan rates.

Figure S8. Comparison under different metrics of the capacitance extracted from the three different NMO materials by Dunn's method, and the purely DLC capacitance of an equivalent electrode with only the current collector and conductive additive (Ketjen). A) Shows the capacitance normalized by the full electrode mass, B) normalized by the active material mass, C) normalized by the geometric area of the electrode and D) normalized by the surface area of the electrodes extracted by BET measurements.

S3. Full flow cell experiments

Figure S9. a) GCDs results and b) SRR of the different NMO materials in the full flow cell in 0.05 M NaCl solution applying 0.05 A g⁻¹ in the ±0.8 V range.

Figure S10. Ageing analysis process using differential capacity analysis (dQ/dV) plots of the different NMO materials, a) to c), after 5 (blue) and 100 cycles (green).

Table S2. XPS analysis results showing the proportions of different manganese oxidation states, the relative abundance of manganese to sodium, and the Mn:O ratios in Mn–O–Mn bonding environments and the total oxygen environment.

Electrode	%Mn ³⁺ : %Mn ⁴⁺	Mn ³⁺ :Mn ⁴⁺	Mn:Na	Mn:O (Mn-O-Mn)	Mn:O (total)
Fresh Na _{0.44} MnO ₂	81.6 /18.4	4:1	3:2	1:2	2:5
Cycled Na _{0.44} MnO ₂	72.7/27.3	3:1	7:1	5:6	1:2
Fresh Na _{0.7} MnO ₂	79.1/20.9	4:1	1:4	1:4	1:6
Cycled Na _{0.7} MnO ₂	76.1/23.9	3:1	---	1:2	3:7
Fresh mp-NMO	78.0/22.0	4:1	1:4	3:5	1:6
Cycled mp-NMO	82.0/18.0	4:1	3:1	2:3	1:2

Figure S11. XPS spectra of Na 1s of mp-NMO.

Table S3. Ion chromatography analyses were conducted on samples collected during GCD cycling of the full-cell mp-NMO using a simulated brackish water electrolyte. Samples were taken at the end of both the charge and discharge processes. The concentrations obtained in mg L⁻¹ were converted to total mass (mg) based on the electrolyte volume. The variations in cation concentrations in the solution and the corresponding specific removal capacity (SRC) values are also provided.

Cation	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Ca ²⁺	Cl ⁻
Charge (mg)	25.9	0.98	3.6	43.7
Discharge (mg)	24.0	0.79	2.8	38.9
Δ (mg)	1.95	0.183	0.851	4.80
SRC (mg g ⁻¹)	69.4	6.5	30.28	170.8

Figure S12. Cycling stability test of mp-NMO in the full flow cell in 0.05 M NaCl solution applying 0.05 A g⁻¹ in the ± 0.8 V range.

Figure S13. Comparison of the CV profiles performed with the the mp-NMO electrode in a three-electrode cell using two different electrolytes: 50 mM NaCl (orange line) and cation mixture (in an electrolyte containing 0.48 M Na⁺, 0.01 M K⁺, and 0.05 M Ca²⁺, with 0.56 M Cl⁻ as the counter ion, purple).